

The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Environmental Performance, and Profitability on the Value of the Company

(Study on companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange 2016-2018)

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of corporate social responsibility, environmental performance, and profitability on firm value. The research period used was 2016-2018. The study uses the concept of Elkington (1997) which mentions three basic points for company sustainability namely environmental, social, and profit which are proxied by CSR, environmental performance, and profitability. The population in this study is companies listed in IDX 2016-2018 periods. The research sample was taken using purposive sampling method that obtained 36 company samples with 108 observational data consisting of companies in the manufacturing sector, the trade service sector and investment, the property and real estate sector, the mining sector, the agricultural sector and the infrastructure, utilities and transportation sectors, in this study using multiple regression analysis test. Based on the results of data analysis it can be concluded that: corporate social responsibility has no effect on firm value, environmental performance has a negative effect on firm value, profitability has a positive effect on firm value.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, environmental performance, profitability, company value.

I. INTRODUCTION

Each company would have the vision to achieve the advantage that maximum, the prosperity of the shareholders so as to maximize the value of the company. The company value reflects the wealth owned by the company as well as shares or other securities. High company value can increase shareholder welfare. With this guarantee of welfare, shareholders will not hesitate to invest.

In general, company value can be influenced by financial factors, financial factors can reflect how the company obtains funds and allocates these funds, so that their use can benefit the company. In addition, to determine the value of a company that has good prospects or not in the future is to see the company's ability to generate profits. Company profit is not only an indicator to measure the value of the company but also to fulfilled the obligations of those with its funds, and is an element in the creation of company value [32].

At this time, in assessing the performance of a company, it is not only judged by financial factors, nonfinancial factors also have a significant influence on company performance which has an impact on firm value, one of the non-financial factors referred to is Corporate social responsibility. Corporate social responsibility is one of the non-financial factors that need to be considered by the management to increase the value of the company as more improve companies, social inequality and damage to the surrounding environment may occur. One example is the case of mudflow that occurred since May 28, 2006 in the Porong area, Sidoarjo. This incident occurred due to an error in gas drilling by PT Lapindo Brantas in exploiting oil and gas in Sidoarjo which caused pollution and environmental damage to the area. which is very broad, but it also turns off the source of livelihood for the surrounding community. To overcome in 2007, the company began to settle compensation to the community, besides that the company also created sustainable development, which in its operations began to pay attention to social empowerment and environmental restoration in order to reduce the negative impact of the business operation.

In terms of sustainable development, it will be guaranteed if the company always looks at the social and environmental dimensions, in addition to pursuing high profits, the company is also obliged to pay attention to and be involved in fulfilling the welfare of the community and contribute actively in preserving the environment [23]. This is

regulated in Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies (PT Law), which was passed on July 20, 2007.

Regulations related to environmental management and preservation are also regulated in Law Number 32 of 2009 concerning Environmental Protection and Management, which are systematic and integrated efforts undertaken to preserve environmental functions and prevent environmental pollution and/or damage which includes planning, utilization, control, maintenance, supervision and law enforcement. The purpose of this research is to test or find empirical evidence that Corporate Social Responsibility, environmental performance, and profitability have a positive effect on firm value.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholders are all internal and external parties who can influence or be influenced by the company either directly or indirectly. Stakeholders are groups of individuals who can influence or be influenced by the success or failure of an organization [27]. The approach to stakeholders, organizations choose to responding to many demands from interested parties, namely every group from the environment outside the organization who is affected by the actions and decisions of the organization [37].

2.2. Legitimation Theory

[12] state that the thing that underlies the legitimation theory is a social contract between companies and communities where the company operates and uses economic resources. Community legitimacy is a strategic factor for companies in developing and advancing companies. Community legitimacy can be seen as something that companies seek from society. With this, the legitimacy of the benefits or potential resource for companies to survive [30].

2.3. The Value of The Company

[11] argues that firm argues that firm value will be reflected in the market price of its shares. [29] state that company value is the price a prospective buyer is willing to pay if the company is sold. The more high-value companies describe the more prosperous is also the owner. The value of the company can increase if the institution is able to become an effective supervisory tool.

2.4. Corporate Social Responsibility

According to [21] Corporate Social Responsibility is a sustainable commitment from a company that runs ethically and contributes to development to improve the quality of life for workers and their families, local communities and the wider community. Corporate Social Responsibility is part of the achievement of the company's three successes, which consist of economic, environmental and social success or what is commonly called the triple bottom line success of a company.

2.5. Environmental Performance

The company's environmental performance is the company's performance in creating a good or green environment [33]. In Indonesia, the implementation of the company's environmental performance is facilitated by the existence of the Company Performance Rating Program (PROPER), which is an instrument used by the Ministry of the Environment to rank companies' compliance with their environmental performance.

2.6. Profitability

According to [2], profitability is the ability of a company to earn profits in relation to sales, total assets and own capital. In general, the company is more like the income that they receive is used as a major source of financing for investment.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

Firm value is the price a prospective buyer is willing to pay if the company is sold. The higher the company value, the more prosperous the owner will be. The Tobin's Q ratio is a measure of firm value used in this study. Tobin's Q calculation refers to the [41], in measuring company value, the formula can be used:

$$\text{Tobin's Q} = \frac{(E \cdot MV + D)}{(TA)}$$

Q	: Company Value
EMV	: Equity Market Value (Closing Price x Number of shares outstanding)
D	: Value Book of Total Debt (Debt Fluent + Debt Current)
TA	: Total company assets

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is the disclosure of social and environmental information in the company's annual report. In measuring this social disclosure the CSD Index is used which is the relative disclosure area of each sample company for its social disclosure. The CSDI calculation formula is as follows:

$$CSDI_j = \sum X_{ij} / n_j$$

- CSDI_j : Corporate Social Disclosure Index company j
- n_j : number of items to be disclosed, n_j = 91
- X_{ij} : number of items disclosed

Environmental performance is the company's performance in creating a good environment. In this research using the PROPER performance rating system, it includes the ranking of companies in five (5) colours, each of which has its own points, as can be seen below:

1. Gold	: very good	score: 5
2. Green	: good	score: 4
3. Blue	: enough	score: 3
4. Red	: bad	score: 2
5. Black	: very bad	score: 1

Profitability is the ability of a company to generate profits within a certain period. In this study, the ratio used to calculate the level of profitability is the ratio proxied by Return on Assets (ROA) which is the company's fundamental performance in terms of efficiency and effectiveness of the company's operations in earning profits [12]. ROA calculation using the formula:

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Earning After Tax (EAT)}}{\text{Total Assets}} \times 100\%$$

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The population in this study are all companies listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) in 2016-2018. Sampling was done by use method of purposive sampling. The sample selection. The sample selection criteria are as follows: Companies that are listed on the IDX and publish annual reports on www.idx.co.id in 2016, 2017 and 2018, IDX companies that report Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the company's annual report, Companies that participate in the PROPER program in 2016-2018. Analysis used descriptive statistics to see the picture or descriptive data that seen from the average value, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum. The descriptive statistical analysis test table can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Y_Tobins_Q	108	0.32	23.29	2.5273	3.56351
X1_CSR	108	0.10	0.64	0.3041	0.1620
X2_KL	108	2.00	5.00	3.1759	0.52647
X3_ROA	108	-11.82	46.59	7.1035	8.52467

Table 2. Multiple Regression Analysis

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients B, t Sig.		
Y_Tobins_Q	1.390	4.613	0.000
CSR	-0.007	-0.015	0.988
KL	-0.221	-2.301	0.024
ROA	0.097	11.084	0.000

Dependent variable :Tobins_Q

The coefficient of determination (R²) in essence measures how far the model's ability to explain the variation of the independent variable on the dependent variable, which can be detected by looking at the coefficient of determination. The following is a table of the R² Determination Coefficient Test:

Table 3. The R² Determination Coefficient Test Results

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square
1	0,790	0,624	0,610

Table 4. Goodness of Fit Test

Model	F	Sig.
Regression	42,120	0,000

Based on table 3, the F test shows that the calculated F value is 42.120 while the F table value is 2.72 (42.120 > 2.72) with a significance value of $\alpha < 0.005$ (0.000 < 0.005) in accordance with the basis for decision making in the F test, it can be concluded that the regression model in this study can explain the relationship between the independent variables, namely CSR, environmental performance, and profitability on the dependent variable, namely firm value.

Table 5. Regression Analysis

Model		t	Sig.
1	(constant)	4,613	0,000
	CSR	- 0.015	0.988
	KL	- 2,301	0.024
	ROA	11,084	0,000

Dependent variables: Tobins_Q

4.1. First Hypothesis Testing

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has a positive effect on company value. Based on table 5, the t count is -0.327 and the t table value is 1.66515 (-0.327 > -1.66515), while the significance value is 0.988, which means the sig value. > 0.05 (0.988 > 0.05), so it can be concluded that the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) variable has no effect on firm value so that the first hypothesis is rejected.

These results state that the company does not communicate social responsibility appropriately so that it has not been captured as something that needs to be considered by interested parties such as investors. In theory, CSR disclosure should be a consideration for investors in investing, because it contains information. social and environmental issues that the company has done. This information is expected to be a consideration for investors to invest [11].

There are indications that investors do not need to see the CSR disclosures made by companies, because there is a guarantee stated in the UU PT No. 40 of 2007, that the company must have implemented CSR and its disclosures, even though the disclosures were still low. In this study cannot prove the concept of the triple bottom line 3P (people, planet, profit) [2], because the concept is only needed by the company is not for investors who prefer the monetary unit.

4.2. Second Hypothesis Testing

Based on table 5, it is obtained t count of -2.301 with t-table of 1.66515 (-2.301 < -1.66515) while the significance value is 0.024 which means the sig value. < 0.05 (0.024 < 0.05), it can be concluded that the environmental performance variable (KL) has a negative and significant effect on firm value but is contrary to the second hypothesis, so that the second hypothesis is rejected.

Of the 108 data processed by researchers, the average company received a blue rating, which means that the company made environmental management efforts only in accordance with what is regulated by law. However, the environmental performance results that can be said to be sufficient do not necessarily guarantee good company performance results. This indicates that stakeholders or the community feel that the results are not in accordance with expectations. They hope that the company can carry out more environmental management than is required by law, such as being able to efficiently utilize resources and implement 3Rs (Reuse, Reduce, Recycle).

Therefore, the environmental performance results from the PROPER rating have not been able to attract stakeholders to invest in the company, but it can reduce the interest of investors to invest their capital. Whereas with the existence of high profit, the company can use it to maximize environmental performance which is expected to get a better rating, namely the gold category from the ministry of environment. but to get a high color rating in PROPER, of course, there are many requirements that the company must meet.

4.3. Third Hypothesis Testing

Based on table 5, the count is 11.084 with a t table value of 1.66515 ($11.084 > 1.66515$) while the significance value is 0.000, which means the sig value. < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), it can be concluded that the variable profitability (ROA) has a positive and significant effect on firm value so that the third hypothesis (H_a) is accepted.

In testing the hypothesis above, it shows that profitability (ROA) has a positive and significant effect on company value on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2016-2018 period. These results are consistent with the theory [16] which states that the company's profitability continues to increase will increasingly be able to improve the ability level of confidence and interest of prospective investors to investments in companies that, because of the essentially investors expect optimal return on investment that is embedded.

In investing in the capital market, investors generally prefer companies that are profitable, because by choosing companies that are profitable, investors believe they will benefit from the results of their investment. ROA is an indicator of profitability that is used to measure a company's ability to generate profits with its assets. The level of ROA depends on the management of the company's assets by management which reflects the efficiency of the company's operations. The higher the ROA, the more efficient and effective the company will be in increasing firm value.

V. CONCLUSION

Corporate social responsibility has no effect on firm value, environmental performance has a negative effect on firm value, profitability has a positive effect on firm value. For a subsequent researcher suggested for use guide to Corporate Social Responsibility which is another example of CSR which is based on ISO 26000 by using the most important categories disclosed by the company, environmental categories, employment, and social but still use the standard date.

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